

JAVASCRIPT DASTURLASH TILINING STANDARD OBYEKT-LARI.

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JavaScript garchi browser tomonidan ko'rishni imkoniyati bor bo'lsa, ham bu dasturlash tili hisoblanadi. JavaScript dasturlash tilini o'rganishingizga bir qancha sababalar va qulayliklar keltirib o'tamiz

JavaScript dunyodagi eng mashhur dasturlash tillaridan biridir.

JavaScript asosan Web dasturchilar ko'p qo'llaydi.

JavaScript o'rganish juda oson.

Nima uchun JavaScriptni o'rganish kerak?

Agar siz web dasturchi bo'lib goh fronend dasturchi bo'lishingizdan qat'i nazar JavaScript ga duch kelasiz. JavaScript asosan front end taraflama ko'p qo'llaniladi. JavaScript bilan siz front end da qo'llashingiz mumkin bo'lgan HTML va CSS script tillarini ham boshqara olasiz.

Tez-tez beriladigan savollar

JavaScript-ni qanday olaman?

JavaScript-ni qayerdan yuklab olsam bo'ladi?

JavaScript bepulmi?

Javoblar:

1. JavaScript ni alohida yuklab olishingiz zarur bo'lmaydi

2. JavaScript allaqochon kompyuteringizda, planshetingizda va smartfoningi brauzeringizda ishlamoqda

JavaScript bepul.

JavaScript 1995 yilda Brendan Eich tomonidan ixtiro qilingan va 1997 yilda ECMA standartning rasmiy nomidir. ECMAScript- bu tilning rasmiy nomi.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida ham boshqa dasturlash tillari singari funksiya mavjud va vasifalari ham o'xshash hisoblanadi. Funksiya uchun qisqacha ta'rif quydagicha eltirsak bo'ladi.

Funksiya- ma'lum bir vazifa bajarishga muvaffaq bo'lib dastur kodining bir qismi hisoblanib uni qayta-qayta foydalanish imkoniyati bo'lib kod bo'lagidir.

JavaScript foydalanish

JavaScript dan foydalanishni bir qancha usuli mavjud bo'lib ulardan biri html sahifani tarkibida foydalanish boshqa bir turi esa tashqi fayil sifatida foydalanish mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, JavaScript kuchli dasturlash tili bo'lib interaktiv va dinamik veb-sahifalar va veb-ilovalarni yaratishda keng qo'llaniladi. Uni o'rganish oson barcha asosiy veb-brauzerlar tomonidan qo'llab quvvatlanadi va boshlanishiga yordam beradigan ko'plab manbalar va ramkalar mavjud. Biroq, mijoz tomonidan skript yaratish bilan bo'liq xafsizlik muammolarini yodda tutish kerak.

JavaScript bilan ishlashda quydagi bir nechta narsalarni yodda tutish kerak:

1)JavaScript voqelarga asoslangan tildir , ya'ni kod tugmani bosish yoki sahifa yuklanishi kabi muayyan hodisalarga javoban ishlaydi. Bu yanada interaktiv va sezgir foydalanuvchi tajribasiga imkon beradi.

2)JavaScript erkin terilgan tildir, ya'ni siz o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilganingizda uning ma'lumotlari turini ko'rsatishingiz mumkin.

3)JavaScript – bu ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan til, ya'ni siz kodingizni tartibga solish va tuzilishi uchun ob'ektlar va sinflarni yaratishingiz mumkin. Bu prototiplar va konstruktorlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

4) JavaScript –da turli hil o'rnatilgan funksiyalar va ob'ektlarni ta'minlovchi boy standard kutibxona mavjud .

Bunga massivlar , satirlar va sanalar ,shuningdek , muntazam ifodalar va taymerlar kabi kengaytirilgan xususiyatlar kiradi.

5) JavaScript ko'pincha dinamik veb-ilovalarni yaratish uchun AJAX va JSON kabi boshqa texnologiyalar bilan birgalikda ishlatiladi. AJAX asinxron veb sahifalarni yaratishga imkon beradi , ular sahifani yangilmasdan yangilanishga imkon beradi , ular sahifani yangilamasdan yangilanishi mumkin. JASON –bu server va mijoz o'rtasida ma'lumotlarni uzatish uchun tez-tez ishlatiladigan engil ma'lumot almashish formati.

6)JavaScript-dan React Native va Electron kabi texnologiyalar yordamida platformalararo ilovalar yaratish uchun ham foydalanish mumkin .

7)JavaScript jonli va faol hamjamiyatga ega, ya'ni o'rganish va boshlashga yordam beradigan ko'plab manbalar va ramkalar mavjud. Bundan tashqari boshqa ishlar chiquvchilar bilan bog'lanishingiz va so'ngi tendentsiyalar va eng yaxshi amalyotlardan xabardor bo'lishingiz mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab konfrensiyalar va uchrashuvlar mavjud.

8)JavaScript –da juda ko'p uchinchi tomon kutibxonalari va ramkalari mavjud bo'lib , ular ishlab chiqish jarayonini soddalashtirish va murakkab ilovalarni yaratishni osonlashtirish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin, masalan, JQuery , Lodash , axios, Moment.js va boshqalar .

9)Nihoyat, JavaScript doimiy ravisgda rivojlanib bormoqda , yangi xususiyatlar va yangilanishlar muntazam ravishda chiqariladi. Til imkoniyatlaridan to'liq foydalanish uchun eng so'nggi yangilanishlardan xabardor bo'lish muhim.

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